

The effectiveness and Utility of Artificial Intelligence on University Teacher's Performance - An Appraisal

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ABSTRACT

The technology has made it easy , but there are challenges too. Back in the days, We would send a letter and Wait for a response for at last 10 days. Now the response has to be there in minutes. On email one can not even miss it , says the experts. A technological expert in the profession for about 20 years says , we have to be prompt with all kinds of information relevant to the office and have to be on our toes. Teacher must know that their hour has arrived - not only because they are in short supply but also because they are indispensable, not with standing artificial intelligence. The teaching community exist to counter propaganda, promote learning, develop thinking, innovative skills, imaginative minds and instill strong values under the inspiring manner to build the worthy citizens of the Nation and the world. We teaching community must wisely use the sweet and exemplary power that we passes.

Keywords :Evolve, Radical,Changes,Finger Tips,Prompt,Requires,Upgrade,Abreast Connectivity

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"All things living are in search of a better world. Men , animals , Plants , even unicellular organisms are constantly active. They are trying improve their situation, or at least to avoid its deterioration.Every organism is constantly preoccupied with the task of solving problems. These problems arise from its own assessments of its condition and of its environments: Conditions which the organism seeks to improve.

- Karl popper

In the past 40 years , the profession has evolved, on those in it have gone through ' radical changes ' several educationist and authorities observed. From shorthand to typewriters. Personal computers, and now hand held devices. The work is at their fingertips and goes on around the clock. The technology has made it easy, but there are challenges too. Back in the days, we would send a letter and Wait for a response for at least 10 days. Now the response has to be there in minutes. On email one cannot even miss it, says the experts. A technological expert in the profession for 17 years says , we have to be prompt with all kinds of information relevant to the office and have to be on our toes"

Technology can aid but cannot replace human touch and hence it is not a dying profession but something that requires an individual touch with upgrade one skills, be organized and stay already technology, many of them believes.

"People are calling it a dying profession because they say artificial intelligence can make presentations or write letters. But that is not enough because AI does not have the human touch. AI can get you the procedures and help in making preparations, but it is an individual who would understand the companies USP and build on that. But the tools only aid me and at the end of the day, it my presentation and I am accountable for the results.

- Coelho

Further, Parnab Mookherjee give emphasis "All things living are in search of a better world. Men , animals , Plants , even unicellular organisms are constantly active. They are trying improve their situation, or at least to avoid its deterioration.Every organism is constantly preoccupied with the task of solving problems. These problems arise from its own assessments of its condition

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Further, Parnab Mookherjee give emphasis by narrating, " If it were only about technology, a website would serve all the purposes. But when certain companies want to invest in your company. They want to know more about it from us and understand the employee boss - management equation " To ensure continuous access to digital resources, strong internet connectivity and devices must be prioritized.

The education system plays a significant role in developing a culture of innovation. Emphasis on bookish , rote and information dumping - based

learning does not spark innovation. During the colonial period, the British statically replaced the traditional Indian education system with a system that abnegated children from their environment and we are still suffering for it. Hopefully, the New Education Policy (NEP) will help to reignite minds and encourage them to act on issues that confront society Rabindranath Tagore was a torch - bearer for such a process when he set up Shantiniketan.

There was a time when the teacher used to share information and analysis. Now students get them online. So the classroom activities had to be changed. Now the teachers tell specific students to come prepared on a topic and make a presentation on their understanding. The students are more connected with the topics being taught and the class becomes more immersive. Various teaching methodologies had emerged with advances in technology. Every teacher used a different method make teaching interesting. We explain concepts and call students to solve problems on the board. The experiments of students as Co- instructors is good as long as teaching activities are not entirely past on students. Students taking up the role of teachers and explaining concepts to their classmates has become a regular mode of learning at the various central universities. As an educationist has tightly narrated on the concept as "students as co - instructor pedagogy", which has been introduced this year to keep students engaged in teaching learning activities. From amongst the students, one will be a co - instructor for a particular concept. The students explains the concept for 15 - 20 minutes in front of their students. The teacher then takes the lesson toward. Every student gets an opportunity by rotation. The universities introduced the modal to counter classroom monotony among students, who rely heavily on online platforms to understand concepts.

A teacher touches eternity , the influence of the good teacher can never be erased " Teaching is the profession that teaches other professions , a good teacher can inspire, hope ignite the imagination and in stile a love of learning." and thus it goes on. The teachers should have an insight to change the curriculum as & when it required as per the situation and interests of the

younger generations of the advanced world.

Teachers, as believed, should be active participants in all policy making that applies to school education. They are the ones who are actually in the field. So they would get to know the gaps and the practical difficulties and thus understand the kind of reforms required from time to time in our education system and the assessment modes. We realize that the need to update with greater frequency has become urgent. Past reforms have shown that the state officials and the higher education academics are not equipped to handle these tasks on their own. Teachers should be aware of their own importance and must not limit their activism to pay scales.

The genuine concern about the nature of their work and what they are expected to deliver. Teachers, in the modern era, must realize that the classroom is their kingdom and the floor therein is their stage where they must be powerful actors. The student's impressionable minds absorb ideas like a sponge. When they are older, they will remain teachers of what they remember of their lessons years ago. No wonder, political leaders go all out to capture young minds by monitoring text - books contents and designing the curriculum. In politically sensitive times, school teachers and college professors are arrested for 'sedition' when the ruling dispensation feels threatened.

Teachers must know that their hour has arrived - not only because they are in short supply but also because they are indispensable, not withstanding artificial intelligence. Their work is certainly not just 'to cover the syllabus' or to prepare students for exams and their purpose is definitely not to indoctrinate. The teaching community exist to counter propaganda, promote learning, develop thinking, innovative skills, imaginative minds and instill strong values under the inspiring manner to build the worthy citizens of the Nation and the world. We teaching must wisely use the sweet and exemplary power that we possess. With the advent of new technologies, the artificial intelligence is being used to address inequalities in access to knowledge and research. In 2003, the government announced plans to set

up centers of excellence in artificial intelligence for agriculture, health and sustainable cities. A consortium led by AIIMS - Delhi, IIT Kanpur and IIT - Ropar had been selected for setting up centers for excellence in AI. The research and technology development outputs from these consortia are envisaged to be integral government schemes across these sectors, ensuring that innovations translate into actionable solutions for public benefits.

Conclusion:

The teachers must know that their hour has arrived - not only because they are in short supply but also because they are indispensable, notwithstanding artificial intelligence. Their work is certainly not just 'to cover the syllabus' or to prepare students for exams and their purpose is definitely not to indoctrinate. The teaching community exist to counter propaganda, promote learning, develop thinking, innovative skills, imaginative minds and instill strong values under the inspiring manner to build the worthy citizens of the Nation and the world.

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